

COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT

Transforming Research through Innovative
Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

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D8.2 – COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT

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Communication Toolkit

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0.0	Marina Angelaki, EKT	First draft of Deliverable, including Style Guidelines
0.1	Stefanie Pohle, MWS	Revision of first draft
0.2	Marina Angelaki, EKT	Updated version submitted for review by project partners
0.3	Stefanie Pohle, MWS; Judith Schulte, MWS; Suzanne Dumouchel, HumaNum; Emilie Blotiere, CNRS; Eliza Papaki, Dariah; Vanja Komljenovic, CESSDA; Paula Forbes, AU	Revision of Deliverable and Style Guidelines

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Publishable Summary

The Deliverable presents the visual identity and the communication and dissemination materials created for the TRIPLE project (“Communication Toolkit”). It has been developed in coordination with Task 8.1 (“Project Dissemination and Communication”).

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1 | HOW TO USE THIS DOCUMENT

The Communication Toolkit is a guide to the dissemination and communication materials shared with all project partners. It comprises the project’s visual identity presented in the form of a Style Guidelines (PDF document) and the actual toolkit with the materials (e.g. logo files and document templates).

All materials:

- are in open format so that it is possible to adapt them during the course of the project;
- are provided under an open license (usually Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License);
- are aligned with the visual identity of the OPERAS research infrastructure and other projects developed by OPERAS.

The toolkit is expected to include other items as the project evolves, taking into account emerging needs. The Communication Toolkit has been prepared by EKT in close cooperation with Task 8.1 “Project Dissemination and Communication” that in turn focuses on developing TRIPLE’s communication and dissemination plan and strategy. One outcome of Task 8.1 has been the set-up of the TRIPLE website (<https://www.gotriple.eu/>) and social media channels (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn) as described in Deliverable 8.1 (“Public website and social media channels registered”). For these communication channels it is essential to have visual materials (e.g. banners) in order to create a consistent and recognisable corporate identity image.

TRIPLE’s visual identity and dissemination materials are also aligned with those of the OPERAS Research Infrastructure (OPERAS RI) as well as other services implemented by OPERAS.

2 | OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT

The toolkit includes communication and dissemination materials to be used by project partners. All related materials are shared with project consortium members via the project's Google Drive Folder. A special section will be created in the project website to include materials that will be accessible to third parties (such as project logo, poster, leaflet, project presentation).

The communication and dissemination materials have been created by EKT's graphics design team.

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3| MATERIALS

3.1 Project Logo/Favicon

TRIPLE’s visual identity has been prepared by EKT and approved by the project coordinator and MWS (leader of WP8 “Communication and Dissemination”). In particular, the following items have been prepared and shared with project partners:

- Logo
- Favicon

The TRIPLE logo consists of a symbol and the wordmark “Triple” which are used as a unit. The symbol is in the shape of three overlapping drops symbolising the figure “three” implied in the acronym. The colours purple, red and yellow allude to the visual identity of OPERAS as the overarching research infrastructure and of the project’s coordinating partner (HumaNum). The colours merge in the middle of the logo to express the blending/ merging of the three main types of data (research publications and data, research profiles, projects) that users will be able to discover through the TRIPLE platform.

The project logo has been developed for use in colour or negative, alongside the EU emblem on all project materials. The manual to support project partners in the use of the visual identity materials is provided in the Style Guidelines, included in this report in Annex 1.

3.2 Slogans

In an effort to communicate better the project's key message, project partners have been asked to advise on slogans and subsequently vote their most preferred one(s). The slogans that received the most votes are the following:

- Slogan Type 1: **"TRIPLE - Discover. Connect. Collaborate"** (11 out of 19 votes)
- Slogan Type 2: **"TRIPLE - The multilingual discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities"** (7 out of 19 votes)

It was decided that both slogans will be used for communication purposes. The first one is a short, catchy one, capturing the essence of the project. To achieve this, it uses verbs in the imperative form. The second slogan is longer, providing more information which is not yet expressed through the tagline.

Discover Connect Collaborate

The multilingual discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities

3.3 Banners

Banners have been created for the TRIPLE website and social media channels, but can also be used in other communication and promotional materials. We have created one main banner variant for the website header image, along with others to be used for other purposes as outlined below. These alternatives are all inspired by the project’s visual identity and offer combinations of visuals with text, i.e. the explanation of the acronym “TRIPLE” and the two slogans.

Triple
Transforming Research through Innovative Practices
for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

Home Project Partners Project Deliverables News Contact

TRIPLE consists of a consortium of 18 partners
from 12 European countries and is coordinated from France by Huma-Num

	Abertay University, UK	abertay.ac.uk
	Coimbra University, PT	ucp.pt/en
	Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives (CESSDA) ERIC, Norway; - Slovenian Social Science Data Archives (UJ-ADP) - Finnish Social Science Data Archives (UTTA-FSD) - UK Data Archive (as UK Data Service) (UKDS)	cessda.eu adp.fdsu.uio.no/eng fdsu.uta.fi/en ukdataservice.ac.uk
	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) ERIC, FR	darlah.eu
	EGI, NL	egi.eu
	European Research Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technology (CLARIN) ERIC, NL	clarin.eu
	French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS), FR; - Huma-Num - OpenEdition	cnrs.fr/index.php/en huma-num.fr opendition.org

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	Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) ERIC, FR	darlah.eu
	EGI, NL	egi.eu
	European Research Infrastructure for Language Resources and Technology (CLARIN) ERIC, NL	clarin.eu
	French National Center for Scientific Research (CNRS), FR; - Huma-Num - OpenEdition	cnrs.fr/index.php/en huma-num.fr opendition.org

TRIPLE BANNER 1400X500px for promotional use

Triple

Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration

Discover
Connect
Collaborate

The multilingual discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities

TRIPLE: Promo BANNER 900X500px for FACEBOOK / TWITTER / NEWS

Discover
Connect
Collaborate

The multilingual discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities

Discover
Connect
Collaborate

The multilingual discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities
Discover **Connect** **Collaborate**

The multilingual discovery platform for the social sciences and humanities

Discover
Connect
Collaborate

TRIPLE: COVER for FACEBOOK 1920X1080px / TWITTER 1500x500px

3.4 Flyer 290x204mm

A first version of the TRIPLE project flyer with concise information about the project has been uploaded to the project's Google Drive Folder, to the project website and to a number of partner websites. Moreover, hardcopy versions have been printed and distributed at various events.

The flyer is coloured, two-sided and folds.

3.5 Poster Template

A poster template has been created to be used by project partners for presenting the TRIPLE project at conferences and workshops. It can be used as an online version or be printed up to size A0.

3.6 Presentation Template

A presentation template has been created and will be used by project partners for the development of presentations of the project and its results in various events.

3.7 Deliverable Template

A template for the deliverable documents has been developed (Word file). In addition, a Google Doc template will be created in order to facilitate collaborate writing process involved in the creation of the deliverables.

The preferred font for the body text is Calibri and Calibri Light for headings.

4| STYLE GUIDELINES

The Style Guidelines describe and explain the TRIPLE logo and slogans, the typography and the colour scheme to be used to present the TRIPLE project. It is a separate document, which is attached to this deliverable document (Annex 1).

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5| OTHER INFORMATION

5.1 Links with OPERAS

Since TRIPLE is one of the services of OPERAS, the visual identity aligns with the OPERAS research infrastructure and other projects developed by OPERAS. This is ensured by the design of the project logo which features three overlapping drops in turn symbolizing the OPERAS three platforms. In addition, the three colors used, purple, red and yellow, have been inspired from the visual identities of OPERAS and Huma-Num.

5.2 Visibility of EU Funding and Disclaimers

In accordance with the obligations regarding the dissemination of results, as stated in the Grant Agreement, all project materials produced in the context of the project (publications, website, flyer etc.) must acknowledge EU funding and should be accompanied by the EU emblem and the following text: “This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 863420”.

The Grant Agreement also states that “any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author’s view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”. The following disclaimer will be used in all TRIPLE dissemination materials:

“The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the TRIPLE consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

5.3 TRIPLE versus Triple

TRIPLE (with capital letters) is the project acronym which stands for “Transformative Research through Innovative Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration”. The capitalized version of the wordmark “TRIPLE” is used in running text and document headings.

“Triple” is used in all cases where the project name appears as a graphic/visual element (e.g. as part of the logo) or as part of the name of one of the social media accounts (e.g. @TripleEU).

STYLE GUIDE LINES

Transforming Research through Innovative
Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

story & concept

TRIPLE was launched in October 2019. It will be one of the dedicated services of OPERAS, the Research Infrastructure supporting open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities (SSH) in the European Research Area.

Triple

is an acronym:

Transforming **R**esearch Through **I**nnovative
Practices for **L**inked Interdisciplinary **E**xploration

Minimum size allowed

The minimum recommended size of the logo (along with the description) is $h = 30$ mm.

The minimum recommended size of the logo (without the description) is $h = 10$ mm

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Logo Variation

Please make sure that logo elements changes are avoided. You can only choose between these 2 logo variations for portrait and / or landscape usage.

Protection Zone

Typography

Triple

The typeface that is used for the logotype design and is recommended for the proper reproduction and use of the total visual identity is **Arial Rounded MT Bold**.

Transforming Research Through
Innovative Practices For Linked
Interdisciplinary Exploration

The typeface that is used for the description is **Open Sans Light**

Download it at: <https://fonts.google.com/specimen/Open+Sans?selection.family=Open+Sans>

Color Variation 1

Please make sure that color changes are avoided.

CMYK:

■	C:0	M:100	Y:100	K:0
■	C:50	M:90	Y:0	K:40
■	C:0	M:35	Y:85	K:0

RGB

■	R:237	G:28	B:36
■	R:98	G:33	B:102
■	R:251	G:176	B:64

Color Variation 2

Please make sure that color changes are avoided.
The negative version of the logo is strongly recommended
as seen below.

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Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

PANTONE: PANTONE 185C
PANTONE 2622C
PANTONE 137C

Transforming Research through Innovative
Practices for Linked Interdisciplinary Exploration

GRAY: Black 100%, 70% , 30%

Color Variation 3

Please make sure that color changes are avoided.
The negative version of the logo is strongly recommended
as seen below.

Color Variation 3

The negative version of the logo is strongly recommended as seen below.

